

EDITORIAL

What Negative Effects Can Hormones Used Continuously Cause to the Patient?

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From time to time, the author sees patients who stay menstruating outside their menstrual period or having colic pain during the cycle and for this reason they go to the gynecologist and they sometimes prescribe hormones. Some patients say that they took hormones without having a break for those who menstruate a lot and there are patients nowadays who stay for years and years taking this hormone without menstruation break [1].

This is one of the situations in which it is important to understand what Western Medicine see about this uninterrupted menstruation cycle and what Chinese medicine say about this circumstances [1].

The author is using the reasoning in traditional Chinese medicine due to two reasons. First, because the author usually follows what Hippocrates says, “that is important to consider other ancient medical traditions prior to the knowledge we have nowadays”. The second reason is that, show likes what Albert Einstein said in one quote that is “We can not solve our problems with the same thinking we used when we created them”. So, the author will use another kind of reasoning different used nowadays to see if this type of treating patients will cause some problems to the patients’ health [2,3].

According to traditional Chinese medicine, episodes of menstrual cramps are related to a retention of Cold inside the wombs [4].

This Cold is may be related to the imbalance of internal energy that patients can be generate by inadequate nutrition eating habit such as eating many raw food (that has Cold energy) such as eating raw vegetables and fruits, exposure to Cold or sitting on the floor constantly, walking barefoot, washing your hair and do not dry adequately after washing it, drinking Cold or ice water constantly, such as drinking too much orange juice for example. According to Chinese medicine, in all this situations, there is Cold energy entering inside the body of women and leading to Cold retention inside the uterus, causing abdominal colic and menstrual colic. This situation cannot be solved with the use of hormones and the use of this kind of medication nowadays has some important side effects, not only regarding to the propensity to have cancer or abnormal blood clot but due to the changes in the pattern of all human being, after the implantation of the 5G technology, the human are with less energy inside the body and the use of this kind of hormones, can harm even more this less energy situation and aggravate the delicate energy situation and cause more problems in near future. This problem is well discussed in the article the author (2021) wrote entitled *Is There a Greater Risk in The Use of Hormones Nowadays?*

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and in the article *Is the Population in the World the Same as in the Past?* [4-6].

The author in one of her research (2021) published entitled *Energy Alterations and Chakras' Energy Deficiencies and Propensity to SARS-CoV-2 Infection*, she analyzed 1000 patients chakras' energy centers from 2015 to 2020 and the result was that more than 90% of her patients have no energy in the chakras' energy centers (that corresponds to the five massive organs in traditional Chinese medicine) [5].

Chakras are energy concentrations that the body has and their function are important to bring energy to the operation of various organs and systems in the body. They are not visible by the naked eyes but we can notice their existence because one of the causes of loss of functioning of some organ is happening inside the body, such as when the people are claiming of do not hearing adequately or do not seeing any more, this could be one kind of situation saying that the battery responsible for hearing (second chakra or Kidney according to traditional Chinese medicine) and vision (first chakra or Liver according to TCM) is not working adequately and using this kind of thinking, the only thing that we need to do is to give proper amount of energy again, that the organ needs to work, and reestablish the whole normal mechanism of the body functioning. According to Hippocrates "disease is a natural process; that the signs and symptoms of a disease were caused by the natural reactions of the body to the disease process and that the chief role of the physician was to aid the natural resistance of the body to overcome the metabolic imbalance and restore health and harmony to the organism" [2,7,8].

The lack of understanding of the existence of energy systems by Western medicine causes errors in the diagnosis and consequently in the treatment of these patients because nowadays people are only looking at the matter side of the body and the other side, that is constitute by energy, they cannot understand and due to this ignorance, the patient could not receive the best treatment for that moment and also, can aggravate nowadays, due to the kinds of medications prescribed in this situation, can harm the internal energy, that is altered due to the changes caused by the electromagnetic waves in the whole world. In the article, *Is the Population in the World the Same as in the Past?* the author is showing the importance of changing the type of medication due to this new changes in the energy patten in the human being [6].

In a study written by the author (2021) published in the article *Why is Infertility So High Among Couples Nowadays?* the author demonstrates one of the causes of the reduction in chakra energy being responsible for reproduction and sexuality problems and this could be the main reason for these kind of problems nowadays, but many times, there is no alteration in the laboratory exams and they are usually taxed that are normal. But as these alterations are in the energy level, they cannot appear in the beginning of the energy alteration, only after some years of this alteration

(5, 10 or 20 years of energy imbalances), to alter in the laboratorial exams [9,10].

Therefore, due to the change in energy pattern, the author in this article is showing that the hormones used by women in the past, must be done very carefully nowadays, because due to this changes in people's energy pattern, which can cause the most varied manifestations. In the article she wrote (2021) entitled *Is There a Greater Risk in The Use of Hormones Nowadays?*, the author demonstrates two cases of patients who were using hormones as a contraceptive (in the first patient) and the second as a regulator of the menstrual cycle. The first developed has a thrombosis cavernous sinus and the second developed a nervous central system vascular stroke. Both patients had chakras' energy centers very deficient in energy and both are using Chinese tools and replenishing the chakras' energy centers with highly diluted medications according to the theory created by the author *Constitutional Homeopathy of the Five Elements Based on Traditional Chinese Medicine* to replenish these energies that were one of the reasons for this bad evolution and that worsened with the use of hormones [9].

Menstruation in traditional Chinese medicine represents overflowing of the excess of production of blood by the womens body every month [11].

In an article published by the author (2021) entitled *Energies Alterations and Chakras' Energies Deficiencies as One Cause of Abnormal Uterine Bleeding in Women*, she talks about the energy causes of potencies that have normal bleeding, the author states that the abnormal bleeding presented by these women may be due to the lack of energy in the chakras' energy centers and formation of internal Heat and menstruation may be only one valve to eliminate the excess Heat production found in these energy-deficient patients [12].

The treatment of these patients, replenishing with chakras' energy centers deficient in energy with highly diluted medications, such as homeopathies according to the theory *Constitutional Homeopathy of the Five Elements based on Traditional Chinese Medicine*, is an important tool used by the author to treat the cause and not just treating the symptoms. Using this kind of treatment, we can treat the cause of this bleeding, that is the energy deficiencies and also, prevent the patient to do not have another disease that could develop because of this deficiency, such as diabetes, hypertension, cancer od many other diseases, also published by the author in many other articles [7,10,13-15].

The lack of understanding of how diseases are produced in terms of energy has led to causing more harm to the patient's energy because with simple changes in diet and guidelines on how to prevent not sitting on the cold floor, drinking cold drinks, many times with ice, and eating raw fruits and raw leaves, are very harmful to patients that has colic in menstruation, for example [16].

Patients that is using hormones without interruption, can reduce the chance of the body to release the Heat that is formed when the body is weak in energy (that is quite the entire population nowadays) and for this reason, the patient can keep this Heat inside the body, and complicate in the future since many diseases (infectious and not infectious such as diabetes, hypertension, cancer etc., all came from energy deficient with Heat retention) [7,10,14].

That is why we need to integrate the two kinds of medicines that exist today and do the reformulation of the entire medical curriculum that exist today, because the doctors that we are training to treat our patients are not learning to use medications that cannot harm our health nowadays, in the contrary, they are teaching to use more highly concentrated medications, that can reduce even more this energy that is already low and cause more deleterious effect or even death, as the author (2021) showed in her recent publications entitled *Is the Medication used in Intubation of Patients with Covid-19 Affecting the Outcome of the Patient's Treatment?* [17].

So, the whole understanding the entire human being, since the energy formation to the matter part it is very important nowadays to prevent further complications and deaths due to our ignorance [17].

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